

New Aspects of Split Disk Test Method for Filament Wound Structures

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the behavior of the filament wound ring specimens was analyzed for the split disk test by finite element method with the effect of friction between the split disk fixture and the ring specimen. But the effect of friction can be eliminated by averaging the moduli for loading and unloading state with maintaining the same crosshead rates. Tensile moduli were evaluated for filament wound ring specimens by split disk test and compared to the theoretical values obtained by the rule of mixtures. The measured elastic moduli of ring showed very good agreement with the theoretical values when the strain gages are applied at properly selected positions in the ring.

INTRODUCTION

The filament wound structures can be made by wet winding method using the impregnated reinforcing fibers or by dry winding method using the B-stage prepreg tows over a mandrel. This processing methods are applicable to rocket motor cases, high pressure gas tanks, aircraft fuselages, radomes, launching tubes for guided missiles, etc. The first step of shape design of filament wound structures is netting analysis in which only the reinforcing fibers are assumed to carry all the loads by tension without consideration of matrix resin[1]. The structural performance is so highly influenced by the tensile properties of the constituent materials used in the design that the tensile properties must be evaluated properly with consideration of the characteristics of filament winding process.

Though numerous evaluation methods have been studied for the tensile properties of fiber reinforced composites, these properties are usually measured using flat specimens which are simple to prepare and test. But filament wound structures are different from the general fiber reinforced composites in shape and the continuity of the reinforcing fibers. The measurement of tensile properties, including tensile modulus and tensile strength, of filament wound structures has been a special interest to the composite designer for tens of years. Several test methods such as the pressurized filament wound vessel test[2], the pressurized ring test[3], the split disk test[4], and tensile test of coupon specimen manufactured by filament winding [5] are used to evaluate tensile properties of filament wound structures. Among these, split disk test of filament wound ring is simple and does not need complicated pressuring jigs, and can test the 'as wound' ring specimen. However, it has been known that the testing of the filament wound ring specimen by split disk method is not applicable to its modulus measurement, but only to the determination of its comparative apparent tensile strength. This is due to the stress concentration by local bending around the edges of split disks and the friction between the ring specimen and the test fixture[6]. This research studied the modification of split disk fixtures and measurements of tensile modulus in the fiber direction of ring specimens. The behavior of the filament wound ring specimens was analyzed for the split disk test by finite element method with the effect of friction between the split disk fixture and the ring specimen. The measured tensile properties were compared to the theoretical values from the rule of mixtures.

FINITE ELEMENT MODELING

The finite element analysis was conducted to verify the applicability of the split disk test for the modulus measurement of the ring specimen. The distributions of deformation and stress in the ring specimen were determined considering the friction between the ring specimen and the test fixture.

The split disk test employs a thin, circular ring as a specimen to determine tensile properties of filament wound structures as shown in Fig.1. The standard dimensions of the ring specimen are given in ASTM D2290[4]. The split disk test fixture has a semi-circular shape and the ring specimen is mounted on a well-aligned test fixture installed on the tensile testing machine. Most of the inner surface of the ring specimen keeps in contact with the test fixture.

A quarter of the specimen-fixture assembly was taken into account because of the symmetry of loading and geometry as shown in Fig.2. A quarter of the ring specimen was modeled by 1000 four node isoparametric solid elements. The test fixture was modeled by contact surface elements which are a kind of gap elements. Boundary conditions are applied to simulate the semi-circular shaped test fixture. The inside node on the vertical axis of the ring specimen is fixed and the other nodes on the vertical axis are allowed only to displace along the vertical axis. The nodes on the horizontal axis are tied together in vertical displacement, i.e., all the nodes have the same vertical displacement due to the symmetry with respect to the horizontal axis. All the nodes on the inside surface of the ring specimen which contact the test fixture surface may displace only tangentially to the test fixture. The external load is applied to the node on the horizontal axis in the form of a set of nodal forces. The material properties of the ring specimen are those of T300/5208[7]. Under these conditions, ANSYS 4.4A was used for the finite element analysis.

Fig. 3 shows the load-strain relations obtained from the finite element analysis at each gage location during both loading and unloading paths for the case with no friction ($\mu=0.0$) and the case with friction ($\mu=0.05$). The results reveal that hysteresis loops occur at each gage location due to the friction between the ring specimen and the test fixture. It is interesting that the friction effect increases as it is farther away from the test fixture edge. The hysteresis loop due to the friction effect is located almost symmetrically with respect to the specific slope, which is expected from load-strain curves for the case with no friction. Therefore, the friction effect can be eliminated by taking the mean slope of loading and unloading curves.

Table 1 shows the predicted modulus of the ring specimen at each gage location calculated by Equation (2) for the case with no friction. The input modulus in the fiber direction of the ring specimen is 181.0 GPa, which is that of T300/5208. The analysis result shows that the modulus can be predicted at any locations within 1.1% error of the input modulus except the local bending region around the test disk edges. Table 2 shows the predicted modulus of the ring specimen at each gage location for the case with friction ($\mu=0.05$). In this case, the predicted modulus during the loading path is higher than the input one at each gage location, but the reverse is true during the unloading path. For the evaluation of tensile modulus of the ring specimen, the friction effect can be also eliminated by taking the mean value of loading and unloading paths. The analysis result shows that the modulus can be predicted within 0.7% error of the input modulus at any locations except the local bending region.

RING SPECIMENS AND TEST FIXTURE

T300 graphite fibers were used for the reinforcement of the ring specimens. The binding matrix was composed of AD6005 epoxy, hardener(H3326), and accelerator(DY062). The filament wound ring specimens were prepared according to ASTM D2291[8]. Fig. 4 shows the shape of split disk fixtures used for characterization of tensile properties of the ring specimens. Fig. 4(a) shows the original fixture design[4] and Fig. 4(b) shows the modified one. The original fixture can align the ring specimen with the loading direction through the universal joint. But the rotation of fixture about the universal joint bring about bending in width direction of the ring specimen, especially around the split disk edges of the fixture when the load level is high. This non-uniform stress distribution in width direction is connected to the underestimation of the failure load of a ring specimen. The modified fixtures are so rigidly fixed to the loading ram that the fixtures do not rotate out of plane of the disks and reduce the local bending in width direction. The alignment of the loading direction of the two split disks are greatly improved through pin holes attached at the horizontal matching surfaces. Table 3 shows the mechanical properties of the fiber and resin matrix used for the ring specimen. The tensile modulus of the fiber was

measured by a strand test of the fibers[9], which showed far less values than those of suppliers.

EVALUATION OF TENSILE MODULUS

The specimens were loaded using a hydraulic test machine(Instron 1335) and the modified split disk test fixture shown in Fig. 4(b). The crosshead was displacement controlled to 1.0 mm/min. The tensile test using split disk test is influenced by the loading alignment and the friction between the specimen and the fixture. In this study, the alignment of loading direction was greatly improved through the pin at the horizontal matching disk surfaces. The friction between the ring specimen and fixture surface was minimized by applying graphite powders, where P and A stand for applied load and cross-sectional area of ring specimen around split disk edges, respectively. The fiber volume fractions were measured with matrix digestion method[10]. The measured volume fraction was 58% for T300/AD6005. The rule of mixtures are known to predict the tensile properties very accurately using the constitutional material properties and the fiber volume fraction. The finite element analysis of split disk test[6] showed that the applied tensile loading to the split disks brings the local bending in thickness direction of the ring specimen around the disk edges and this yields stress concentration.

The ring specimen was instrumented with eight strain gages (KYOWA KFG-2-120-C1-11) along the circumferential direction as shown in Fig. 1. The first three strain gages near the test fixture edge were 7.5 degrees apart and the other strain gages were 15 degrees apart from each other. Before placing the ring specimen on the test fixture, carbon powders were evenly spread over the contact surface of the test fixture to reduce the possible friction between the ring specimen and the test fixture. When the split disks are pulled apart, the load is applied to the ring specimen and produces an average equivalent internal pressure loading. The applied load signal and eight strain gage signal were recorded digitally by a data acquisition system. The apparent tensile stress of ring specimen can be determined from Equation (1).

$$\sigma_{app} = \frac{P}{2A} \quad (1)$$

The modulus at each gage location, E_g are calculated by Equation (1) and Equation (2).

$$E_g = \frac{\sigma_{app}}{\epsilon_g} \quad (2)$$

where ϵ_g is the strain at each gage location.

As can be conceived, the circumferential strain distribution in the ring specimen is influenced by the friction between specimen and fixture surface and local bending around the disk edges. To eliminate the frictional effect on the strain distribution, the strain was measured for both loading and unloading paths with maintaining the same crosshead rates. The friction acts reverse to the direction of the relative slip of the ring specimen to the disk surface. This friction has the effect of reducing the load when the load is increasing and the reverse is true when the load is decreasing. The frictional effect is the same in magnitude and the opposite in the sense for loading and unloading paths. The tensile modulus of a ring specimen can be determined by averaging the moduli for loading and unloading paths as shown in Equation (3).

$$(E_g)_a = \frac{(E_g)_l + (E_g)_u}{2} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 5 shows the 8 load-strain curves from the 8 strain gages on the surface of a ring specimen made of T300/AD6005. The strain from S.G.1 (strain gage 1) is smaller than that from the other gages S.G.2-S.G.8 due to the local bending for all load levels. The load-strain curves form hysteresis loop for the complete loading and unloading paths due to the friction between fixture surface and ring specimen. The farther the gage location is from the split disk edges, the greater the hysteresis is due to larger contact area.

Table 4 shows the measured tensile moduli from load-strain curves during both loading and unloading

during the loading paths showed higher value than the modulus for the ideal frictionless case. Conversely, the moduli measured during unloading paths showed lower value than that of the frictionless case. The averaged moduli for S.G.2-S.G.8 using the Equation (3) have the maximum of 136.0 GPa and the minimum of 125.0 GPa; the theoretical tensile modulus is 126.7 GPa by the rule of mixtures. Table 4 shows the tensile modulus can be measured within a few percent error by properly selecting the gage locations.

CONCLUSION

In this study, the possibility of the modulus measurement of the ring specimen using the split disk test was investigated through the finite element analysis and experiment. The circumferential strain distribution in the ring specimen was influenced by the friction between specimen and fixture surface. To eliminate the frictional effect on the strain distribution, the strain was measured for both loading and unloading paths with maintaining the same crosshead rates. The load-strain curves formed a hysteresis loop for the complete loading and unloading paths due to the friction between fixture surface and ring specimen. The frictional effect could be eliminated by averaging the two slopes of loading and unloading paths. The tensile modulus of ring specimens was measured within a few percent error from the theoretical value by properly selecting the gage locations. The tensile modulus of ring specimens was measured by the strain gages which are applied away from the disk edges.

According to the results, the split disk test would be a suitable method for the tensile properties measurement of filament wound structures irrespective of the local bending around the test fixture and the friction between the ring specimen and the test fixture.

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Table 1. Calculated modulus of the ring specimen for several gage locations from the finite element analysis (friction coefficient $\mu=0.0$)

Gage location	Modulus in loading path E_l (GPa)	Modulus in unloading path E_u (GPa)	Average modulus $E_a=(E_l+E_u)/2$ (GPa)	Error (%)
1	249.3	249.4	249.4	-
2	182.3	182.3	182.3	0.7
3	181.1	181.1	181.2	0.1
4	180.5	180.5	180.5	0.3
5	179.9	179.9	179.9	0.6
6	180.0	180.0	180.0	0.6
7	180.1	180.1	180.1	0.5
8	178.9	178.9	178.9	1.1

* Input modulus : 181.0 GPa

Table 2. Calculated modulus of the ring specimen for several gage locations from the finite element analysis (friction coefficient $\mu=0.05$)

Gage location	Modulus in loading path E_l (GPa)	Modulus in unloading path E_u (GPa)	Average modulus $E_a=(E_l+E_u)/2$ (GPa)	Error (%)
1	247.3	251.6	249.5	-
2	183.4	181.2	182.3	0.7
3	183.6	178.8	181.2	0.1
4	185.4	176.0	180.7	0.2
5	187.2	173.1	180.2	0.4
6	189.8	171.0	180.4	0.3
7	192.4	169.0	180.7	0.2
8	193.2	166.1	179.6	0.7

* Input modulus : 181.0 GPa

Table 3. Properties of the fiber and matrix used in this study

	Type	Density (g/cm^3)	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Elongation (%)	Volume fraction (%)
Fiber	T300	1.77	Supplied : 235 Measured:216	1.7	58
Matrix	Epoxy	1.21	3.3	6.4	42

Table 4. The measured modulus of the ring specimen of T300/Epoxy for several gage locations by experiments

Gage location	Modulus in loading path $(E_g)_l$ (GPa)	Modulus in unloading path $(E_g)_u$ (GPa)	Average modulus $(E_g)_a = [(E_g)_l + (E_g)_u] / 2$ (GPa)	Error $ E_p - (E_g)_a / E_p$ (%)
1	229.0	239.2	234.1	-
2	126.5	123.5	125.0	1.3
3	130.3	126.2	128.2	1.2
4	132.7	122.3	127.5	0.6
5	137.5	121.0	129.3	2.1
6	143.5	122.0	132.8	4.8
7	149.9	122.0	136.0	7.3
8	147.1	114.7	130.9	3.3

* Predicted modulus E_p : 126.7 (GPa)

Figure 1. Ring specimen

Figure 2. Finite element model

Figure 3. Load-strain curves at several gage locations from finite element result

Figure 4. The original and modified split disk fixtures

Figure 5. Experimental load-strain curves at several gage locations